

CASE REPORT

How to Heal Patient with Multiple Sclerosis

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INTRODUCTION

Multiple Sclerosis (MS) has been defined as an inflammatory demyelinating condition afflicting more than 2.8 million people worldwide. Meta-regression analyses of studies on MS epidemiology since 1965 revealed an almost universal increase in prevalence and incidence of MS over time; and suggest a general increase in incidence of MS in females.

The study for prevalence estimation of MS in Iran in 2013 indicated a high prevalence rate in Isfahan (89 per 100000 of population) and Tehran (88/100000), situated at the central part of Iran (5). Numerous studies revealed that having positive family history of MS can play little role in increasing risk of the disease. The prevalence and incidence of MS widely vary amongst numerous geographical areas and different countries. The current frequency of MS is still unknown in Tehran.

CASE REPORT

Mrs. F.B. aged 41, is a married woman from Western province of Ilam, and was referred to me on 25 Jul. 2020. Her chief complaint was Multiple sclerosis for about 5 years, starting with left hand and left leg paresthesia, and frequency, while she was experiencing her only pregnancy. Her gynecologist said she must undergo caesarian section, since several white patches had been seen and reported in her Brain MRI. Afterwards her spinal cord and back got involved, leading to her left lower and upper limbs limping. She couldn't walk even by a walker and had grown involuntary defecation. She used to suffer from severe obsessive compulsive disorder, before being affected by the motor-sensory symptoms. She was also afraid of infection and microbes. She used to be doubtful, sensitive to her manager's comments. She got angry easily and lost her temper afterwards. She used to inject Zytos every 6 months before covid19 pandemic and 10 mg Dalfyra twice a day [1,2].

METHODOLOGY

An interview was done with her via WhatsApp video call, taking one hour. Her rubrics were analysed by homeopathic diagnostic software, Radar. Causticum lm1 was selected as her constitutional remedy. She started taking Caust. LM1 one drop 3 times daily after 3 vigorous shakes, on July 27 2020. After 2 days, she sent me a text via WhatsApp: "I could not turn my head around because of severe vertigo, but now I can do that without any problem. May coronavirus kill me?! It is killing people badly here!"

I answered him: "Praise to the God for healing your vertigo. Continue taking the remedy as far as you get better and feel good. Do not worry for covid19, because the

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remedy puts your immune system on alert situation, and if you get afflicted by it, it will improve gently.

I asked her on August 3 2020; “Hello Mrs. B. Have you felt any new changes during the last days?”

“Two people would take my arms and limbs to sit me on toilet, previously (before taking the homeopathic remedy), but now I do it myself.” She reported me on August 3 2020.

“Hello Doctor, I went from my room to the toilet by my walker without anyone’s help, I washed my hands and feet and came back to my room. This made my family very happy.”

RESULTS

While Multiple Sclerosis is considered a non-curable autoimmune disease in Conventional Medicine Causticum LM1 homeopathic remedy cured the patient’s vertigo and enabled her motor neurons. Regarding the homeopathic literature, patients with MS have been cured completely or partially by other homeopath colleagues in Iran [3,4].

CONCLUSION

Unfortunately multiple sclerosis prevalence in Iran is the highest among the Middle East countries, during the last decades, due to stressful living in this country. Homeopathy has proved to be an effective method of healing for patients suffering from Multiple Sclerosis. I would like to suggest planning randomized clinical trials to evaluate the role of natural holistic Homeopathic Medicine.

References

- Walton C, King R, Rechtman L, Kaye W, Leray E, Marrie RA, Robertson N, La Rocca N, Uitdehaag B, van der Mei I, Wallin M, Helme A, Angood Napier C, Rijke N, Baneke P. Rising prevalence of multiple sclerosis worldwide: Insights from the Atlas of MS, third edition. *Mult Scler.* 2020 Dec;26(14):1816-1821. doi: 10.1177/1352458520970841. Epub 2020 Nov 11. PMID: 33174475; PMCID: PMC7720355.
- Eskandarieh S, Heydarpour P, Elhami SR, Sahraian MA. Prevalence and Incidence of Multiple Sclerosis in Tehran, Iran. *Iran J Public Health.* 2017 May;46(5):699-704. PMID: 28560202; PMCID: PMC5442284.
- Signs and symptoms are called rubrics in Homeopathic Medicine. 2015.
- Liquid Homeopathic remedies are poeized and stronger by vigorous shaking due to producing energetic bubbles, being shown by Dr. Peter Fisher from England, on an image during 2011 LMHI International Congress in Siri Fort Auditorium in New Delhi India.

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